

Main category	Category	Text section (2.3, 2.4)	Data type/Sub-category	Data format	Data format (recommended for data sharing machines)	Data coverage (global vs Arctic vs regional vs local)	Dimensionality (0D, 1D, 2D, 3D, 4D)	Qualitative vs quantitative	Depth aspect	Time aspect	Date/time of data collection	Comment	Data provider / Data contact	Dataset URL or reference to data paper		
Field geology (6.1)	Sampling	2.3	Sample location and storage. Physical rock samples	Physical rock material	N/A	local	0D	Quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Sample location and purpose. Ideally linked to sedimentary log	Kim Senger	Norwegian Polar Institute repository (Myhre et al. 2020); German National Polar Sample Archive (BGR 2024a); University-internal repositories; NHM		
		2.3	Fossils from Arctic Collections	Physical sample	N/A	Local to Arctic	0D	qualitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Sample location and purpose. Ideally linked to sedimentary log	Jørn Hurum	Nakrem et al. 2023		
		2.3, 2.4	Thermochronological data	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	Local to Arctic	0D, 1D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Apatite (U-Th)/He Apatite Fission Track Zircon (U-Th)/He Zircon Fission Track Muscovite Ar/Ar	Cornelia Spiegel-Behnke	Dallmeyer et al. 1990; Blythe and Kleinspehn 1998; Manecki et al. 1998; Dörr et al. 2012, 2013, 2019b, a; Barnes and Schneider 2019; Schneider et al. 2019; Schaaf et al. 2021; Japsen et al. 2023; Meier et al. 2024		
		2.3, 2.4	Geochronological data (U-Pb, Pb-Pb, Re-Os)	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	Local to Arctic	0D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Absolute dating technique, U-Pb of magmatic bodies, ash layers, and metamorphic units	Anna Sartell, Jaroslaw Majka	Gee et al. 1995; Johansson et al. 2001, 2002, 2004, 2005; Tebenkov et al. 2002; Myhre et al. 2008; Corfu et al. 2013; Midtkandal et al. 2016; Jones et al. 2017; Koglin et al. 2022; Park et al. 2024		
		2.3, 2.4	Geochronological data (Ar-Ar/K-Ar)	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	Local to Arctic	0D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Absolute dating technique	Anna Sartell, Jaroslaw Majka	Gayer et al. 1966; Burov et al. 1977; Vincenz et al. 1981; Birkenmajer et al. 2010; Nejbert et al. 2011; Polteau et al. 2016; Estrada et al. 2024		
		2.3	Oxygen and carbon isotopes	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	0D, 1D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Proxies for palaeoclimate	Valentin Zuchuat, Aleksandra Smyrak-Sikora	Matysik et al., 2017; Jelby et al. 2020, 2025		
		2.3	Rock-Eval	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	0D, 1D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Evaluation of source rock quality	Snorre Olaussen	van Koeverden et al. 2011; Marshall et al. 2015; Koevoets et al. 2016, 2019; Abay et al. 2017, 2022; Uguna et al. 2017; Nicolaisen et al. 2019; Jelby et al. 2020; Janocha et al. 2024		
		2.3	Vitrinite reflectance	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	0D, 1D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Thermal history, coal characterization	Snorre Olaussen	Thronsdén 1982; Abdullah et al. 1988; Orheim et al. 2007; Janocha et al. 2024		
		2.3	Elemental composition	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	0D, 1D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Chemostratigraphy	Snorre Olaussen	Koevoets et al. 2016, 2019; Wesenlund et al. 2022		
		2.4	Detrital zircon provenance	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	Local - regional	0D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Sediment provenance	Cornelia Spiegel-Behnke	Pettersson et al. 2009, 2010; Petersen et al. 2016; Bazarnik et al. 2019; Wala et al. 2021; Anfinson et al. 2022; Klausen et al. 2022		
		2.3	Geochemical data	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	regional	0D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Major and trace elements	Anna Sartell	Bailey and Rasmussen 1997; Sushchevskaya et al. 2009; Nejbert et al. 2011; Ottesen 2015; Jones et al. 2016; Koglin et al. 2022; Estrada et al. 2024		
		2.4	Palaeomagnetic data	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	0D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Magnetostratigraphy and constraining plate tectonic movement	Krzysztof Michalski	Vincenz and Jelenska 1985; Halvorsen 1989; Michalski and Lewandowski 2004; Maloof et al. 2006; Hounslow et al. 2008; Michalski et al. 2012, 2017, 2023; Dudzisz et al. 2016, 2018; Burzyński et al. 2017; Michalski 2018; Zhang et al. 2021		
		2.4	Xenoliths from upper mantle	.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	1D/2D	quantitative	Lower crust/upper mantle	varies	varies	Xenoliths within Neogene/Quaternary volcanic rocks	Sverre Planke	Griffin et al. 2012		
			Sedimentology/stratigraphic logging	2.3	Sedimentary log	.jpg/.png/.tiff	CF-NetCDF	local	1D	qualitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Observations and descriptions of sedimentary units, plus sampling	Sten-Andreas Grundvåg	Dallmann 1999; Midtkandal et al. 2008; Ahlborn and Stemmerik 2015; Olaussen et al. 2018; Rismyhr et al. 2019; Grundvåg et al. 2020; Sorento et al. 2020; Helland-Hansen and Grundvåg 2021
			Structural mapping	2.4	Scanlines, structural data, restorations	.txt/.xlsx	JSON/netcdf	local	2D	quantitative	Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	Mapping of fractures and faults	Kei Ogata	Ogata et al. 2014; Piepjohn et al. 2016; Koglin et al. 2022
	Field sketches/field notebooks	2.3, 2.4	Observations, field data	.jpg/.png/.tiff	CF-NetCDF	local	2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations	Aleksandra Smyrak-Sikora	Arctic Viewer (BGR 2024b)		
	Digital field notebooks	2.3, 2.4	Georeferenced images, notes, orientation data	.mve, kmz, .csv		local	0D to 2D	Quantitative, qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations and documentation	Kim Senger	Senger and Nordmo 2021		
	Field photographs	2.3, 2.4	Images	.jpeg	CF-NetCDF	local	2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations	all			
	Field mapping	2.3, 2.4	Geological maps	.shp, .geotiff	netcdf/geoJSON	regional	2D	qualitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations, sampling	NPI	Dallmann 2015		
	Field mapping	2.3, 2.4	Fault maps	.shp	netcdf/geoJSON	regional	2D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	Observations, structural focus	NPI	Major and Nagy 1972; Braathen et al. 1999; Dallmann 2015		
	Digital geology	2.3, 2.4	Digital outcrop models (SfM)	.obj and others	CF-NetCDF	local-regional	3D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	3D models of outcrops	Peter Betlem, Kim Senger	Betlem et al. 2023, 2024		
	Digital geology	2.3, 2.4	Digital outcrop models (Lidar)	LiDAR	CF-NetCDF	local-regional	3D	quantitative	Surface	varies	varies	3D models of outcrops	Peter Betlem, Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2013; Smyrak-Sikora et al. 2021		

		2.3, 2.4	Photospheres	.jpg, .jpeg	CF-NetCDF	Aerial Local	2.5D	qualitative	surface	varies	varies	2D photography data visualised in 3D.	Rafel Horota	Horota et al. 2023, 2024
		2.3, 2.4	Digital sample/drill core models	.obj	CF-NetCDF	local	3D		Surface or boreholes	varies	varies	3d models of drill cores	Peter Betlem	Betlem et al. 2020
Boreholes and drill cores (6.2)	Borehole data (scientific)	2.3, 2.4	Drill cores	Physical material	N/A	local	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger, Sverre Planke	CO2 wells and exploration wells: Olausen et al. 2019; Senger et al. 2019; DD-1 core sedimentary log: appendix of Zuchuat et al. 2020; Senger et al. 2024a
		2.3, 2.4	Wireline logs	.xlsx, .las	CF-NetCDF	local	1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger	Koevoets et al. 2019; Olausen et al. 2019; Grundvåg et al. 2019
		2.3, 2.4	Technical reports	.pdf, .doc		local	1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies	varies		Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2022, 2024a
		2.3, 2.4	Analyses on drill cores	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF		1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies	varies	Oxygen and carbon isotopes Geochemistry Trace elements Geochronology Rock-Eval / vitrinite reflectance	Aleksandra Smyrak-Sikora	Grundvåg et al. 2014; Dörr et al. 2019a; DD-1 core, raw XRF scan: appendix of Zuchuat et al. 2020; Senger et al. 2024a
		2.3, 2.4	Biostratigraphy						Boreholes and outcrops	varies		Most commonly studied fossils include dinocysts, foraminifera, and ammonites. A database with biostratigraphic data does not exist yet. Majority of the older publication does have only presence/absence or results of semiquantitative analysis provided	Kasia K. Sliwinska	Cenozoic: Manum 1960; Bjærke 1978; Feyling-Hanssen and Ulleberg 1984; Matthiessen 1986; Manum and Thronsdon 1986; Kvaček 1994; Nagy 2005; Golovneva 2010; Nagy et al. 2013 Mesozoic: Spath 1921; Blüthgen 1936; Buchan et al. 1965; Nagy 1970; Ershova 1972; Bjærke and Thusu 1976; Bjærke 1977, 1978, 1980; Bjærke and Manum 1977; Pchelina 1983; Bäckstrom and Nagy 1985; Kopik and Wierzbowski 1988; Århus 1988, 1991, 1992; Smelror and Dypvik 2005; Nakrem et al. 2008; Rogov 2010; Wierzbowski et al. 2011; Midtkandal et al. 2016; Rismyhr et al. 2019; Smelror et al. 2019; Śliwińska and Head 2020; Śliwińska et al. 2020; Hjálmarsdóttir et al. 2022; Rogov et al. 2023; Nøhr-Hansen et al. 2023 Palaeozoic: Vigran 1964; Allen 1967; Nakrem et al. 1992; Mangerud and Konieczny 1993; Buggisch et al. 2001; Luppold 2001; Błażejowski et al. 2006; Błażejowski 2009; Berry and Marshall 2015; Kröger et al. 2017; Lopes et al. 2019, 2021
	Borehole data (commercial)	2.3, 2.4	Drill cores	Physical material	CF-NetCDF?		1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies			SNSK, Trust Artikugol, various petroleum companies	Senger et al. 2023a
	2.3, 2.4	Wireline logs	.xlsx, .las	CF-NetCDF		1D	quantitative	Boreholes	varies			Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2022	
	2.3, 2.4	Technical reports	.pdf	CF-NetCDF		1D	qualitative	Boreholes	varies			Kim Senger, Snorre Olausen	Senger et al. 2022	
	2.4	Heat flow data	.xls	JSON/netcdf		1D		Surface or boreholes	varies			Kim Senger, Alexander Minakov	Global Heatflow Database, Senger et al. 2023b	
Geophysics (6.3)	Magnetotelluric data	2.4	Deep geophysics	.seggy	CF-NetCDF		2D	quantitative	Surface to tens of kms	varies		Alexander Minakov	Beka et al. 2016; Selway et al. 2020	
	Shallow geophysical profiles (ERT, GPR etc.)	2.4	Shallow geophysics	.seggy	CF-NetCDF		2D	quantitative	10s to 100s of meters			Kim Senger	Ignatiuk et al. 2023; Pace et al. 2024	
	Gravity data	2.4	Geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	Local to regional	1D (onshore), 2D (offshore)	quantitative	km-scale			UNIS/NGU, Kim Senger, Marie-Andree Dumais	Olesen et al. 2010; Senger et al. in press	
	Magnetic data (ship-based)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	local	2D	quantitative	Ms to kms			Kim Senger	Senger et al. 2013	
	Magnetic data (aerial)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics	.xlsx	CF-NetCDF	regional	2D	quantitative	Ms to kms			Marie-Andree Dumais, Antonia Ruppel	Olesen et al. 2010; Dumais and Brønner 2020	
	Global seismic tomography	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D/3D	quantitative	Crustal-mantle scale			Wolfram Geissler, Grace Shephard	Schaeffer and Lebedev 2013; Struijk et al. 2018	

	Seismic data (2D)	2.4	Profile-based geophysics on- and offshore	.seggy		Local to regional	2D	quantitative	Uppermost ca 5 km	Shallow vs deep focus Industry vs academia Onshore vs offshore	Wolfram Geissler, Alexander Minakov	Eiken 1985; Johansen et al. 2011; Bælum et al. 2012; Rossi et al. 2018 Data example Pangea: Weigelt and Geissler 2024
	Active seismicity	2.4	Deep to shallow geophysics			Local to regional	0D	quantitative	Surface to epicentre		Alexander Minakov	NORSAR 1971; Köhler et al. 2020; International Seismological Centre 2024
Remote sensing (6.4)	Digital terrain model(s)	2.3, 2.4	Surface		CF-NetCDF	regional	3D	quantitative	surface	Modern and historical models provided	NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute 2014; Porter et al. 2023
	Satellite imagery	2.3, 2.4	Surface	.jpg2000	CF-NetCDF / SAFE / ZARR	regional	3D	quantitative	surface		NPI	Norwegian Polar Institute 2023
	Oblique aerial images (historic)	2.3, 2.4	Surface			regional	2D	quantitative	surface		NPI	toposvalbard.npolar.no
	Bathymetry	2.4	Ocean bottom morphology		CF-NetCDF	regional	3D	quantitative	surface		IBCAO	IBCAO (Jakobsson et al. 2012) Statens kartverket
	Satellite-derived gravity data	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D	quantitative	km-scale		Alexander Minakov	Mémin et al. 2011
	Satellite-derived magnetic data	2.4	Deep geophysics			global	2D	quantitative	km-scale		Alexander Minakov	Olsen et al. 2017; Sabaka et al. 2020.
	inSAR data	2.4	Surface deformation			regional	4D	quantitative	surface		Kim Senger	Rouyet et al. 2024
	GNSS	2.4	Surface deformation			local	4D	quantitative	surface		Halfdan Kierulf	Kierulf et al. 2022
Data integration and data products (6.5)	Palaeogeographic maps	2.3	Maps with a temporal component			regional	2D	qualitative	surface		Sten-Andreas Grundvåg	Smelror et al. 2009; Dallmann 2015
	Digital plate tectonic reconstructions	2.4	Temporal	Gplates		Regional to global	4D	quantitative	surface		Grace Shephard	Shephard et al. 2013
	Geological cross-sections	2.4	Profiles			Local to regional	2D	qualitative	km-scale			Dallmann 2015 + publications
	Sub-ice topography	2.4			CF-NetCDF		3D	quantitative	km-scale			Fürst et al. 2018
	(educational) Thematic data packages	2.3, 2.4	Integrated data sets	.shp, .jpg, .jpeg, .tiff, .obj			0D-4D	both	varies		Rafael Horota	Horota et al. 2023; Senger et al. 2024b
	Publications	2.3,2.4	Thematically diverse				0D-4D	both	varies		Snorre Olaussen	Steel and Worsley 1984; Harland 1997; Dallmann 1999, 2015; Worsley 2008 Faleide et al. 2024; Lundschieen et al. 2024; Tsikalas et al. 2024; Olaussen et al. 2024; Smelror et al. 2024
	Pre-loaded data packages	2.3, 2.4	QGIS	QGIS project			0D-4D	both	varies		Fenna Ammerlaan	Appendix ADP1, this contribution
		2.3, 2.4	GPlates	GPlates project			0D-4D	both	varies		Fenna Ammerlaan	Appendix ADP2, this contribution

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